

INDRALUPTA- AN AYURVEDIC APPROACH- CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Alopecia areata, an autoimmune condition causing patchy hair loss, is correlated with *Indralupta* one of the kshudra roga in Ayurveda *Indralupta* Causing hair loss on the scalp, face and sometimes on other areas of the body. The pathophysiology of Indralupta is the vitiated Tridoshas and Rakta, affecting the scalp and also blockage of hair follicles with aggravation of Rakta and Kapha which further prevents regrowth of hairs. It is described as Kapalgata Roga by Acharya Vagbhata and as a Kshudra Roga by Acharya Sushruta and Madhava Nidana. Contemporary treatments such as corticosteroids often provide temporary relief with potential side effects and high recurrence rates. This report presents a clinical case demonstrating the effectiveness of Ayurvedic therapies in managing *Indralupta*. A 29-year-old male with recurrent alopecia areata unresponsive to conventional treatment showed complete hair regrowth after

five months of *Virechan therapy*, *Shamana Chikitsa* and *Jalaukavacharana* (leech therapy), with visible follicular regrowth within 30 days and no adverse effects.

KEYWORDS: Indralupta, Alopecia Areata, Ayurvedic management.

INTRODUCTION

Indralupta is a sudden loss of hairs. Vagbhata says the major difference being that in Indarlupta hair fall is sudden where as in Khalitya hair loss is gradual. According to Acharya Sushrut it is Raktapradoshaja vikar,^[1] Included in kshudra roga.^[2] Shirogat vyadhi, kapalgata vyadhi, Shiro-Kapalgata vyadhi According to modern science it is correlated with Alopecia

areata, an autoimmune disease that causes round and smooth patches of hair loss on the scalp along with other body parts.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A 29 years male patient registered by opd no. 20250047239 dated on 07/08/2025 came to opd no.9 Of M.A.Podar Hospital, Worli, Mumabi. He presented himself with a complaints of multiple patches of hair loss on left side of jaw region and since 6 months.

There are no personal history of autoimmune disorders (Like psoriasis, vitiligo, asthma, rheumatoid arthritis ect.) or family history in first degree relation. He had undergone allopathic medicine for 3 months, including oral medications as well as external applications. There was no improvement in hair growth and he approached our hospital for further treatment.

Ashtavidha Pariksha

1	Nadi	88/Min
2.	Mala	samadhankarak
3.	Mutra	Niyamit
4.	Jivha	Saam
5.	Shabda	Spashta
6.	Sparsha	Samsheetoshna
7.	Druka	Prakruta
8.	Akruti	Madhyam

Disease specific examination

Site of involvement	left side of Jaw region
Pattern	3 asymmetrical patches
Skin over the patch	Mild dryness and Reddish
skin Sensation	Normal
Itching	Present

Table 1: General Examination.

Pulse	88 beat/minute, Regular
BP	120/86 mm hg
R.R.	17/min
Temperature	99.40F
Height	75 kg
Weight	168 cm
Appetite	Good
Bowel	Clear
Micturition	5-6 times /day, 1 times at night
Sleep	Disturbed

Tongue	Pallor
Addiction	Nil

Laboratory Investigations

Hb%	15.8gm/dl
Total R.B.C	5.27mil/c.mm
Total W.B.C	6900/cu.mm
<i>Neutrophil</i>	54.%
Lymphocytes	41.%
Eosinophils	2%
Basophil	0%
Monocytes	3%
Bleeding time	1min 24sec
Clotting time	3min 04sec

NIDAN

1. *Lavana rasa atisevana*- Chips, Burger, Pizza, Tomato Ketchup, Mayonnaise.
2. vigil during the night
3. exposure to dust, smoke, and sun, intake of heavy and sour food,
4. anxiety -vitiating of *Raktadhatu* in the head.

SAMPRAPTI

- The deranged Vayu and Pitta having recourse to the roots of the hairs bring about their falling off, while the deranged Rakta and Kapha of the locality fill up those pores or holes, thus barring their fresh growth and recrudescence. The disease is called Indralupta, Rujya or Khalitya.^[5]

• SAMPRAPTI GHATAKA

• Doshha

- Vata: Samana, Vyana
- Pitta: Pachaka Pitta and Bhrajaka Pitta
- Kapha: Tarpaka Kapha

• Dushya

- Dhatu: Rasa, Rakta, Asthi
- Mala: Sweda, Kesha

- Agni: Jatharagni, Rasagni, Asthyagni
- Ama: Rasa, Raktagata Ama
- Srotasa: Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Asthivaha, Swedavaha, Manovaha
- Udbhava: Amashaya
- Sanchara: Rasayani (Rasavaha Srotasa)
- Adhithana: Keshabhoomi
- Rogamarga: Bahya Rogamarga (twak and romakopa)
- **Treatment**
- The patient was clinically diagnosed as case of Indralupta (Alopecia areata) and advised for Panchakarma therapy.
- Virechan karma

1. Deepan pachan

- Aarogyavardhini Vati (250 mg) twice a day before meal with kosha jala.
- Amapachana Vati (500 mg tab) 2 tab twice a day after meal
- Shunthi churn + Vidang churn + Triphala churn – 2 gms BD
- Krimikuthar rasa-250 mg tab twice a day after meal.
- Jayapal beej lepan.

GIVEN FOR 7 DAYS

2. Abhyantar Snehapan – with Panchtikta ghrita 30 ml-60 ml – 90 ml-120 ml-150 ml

3. Sarvang snehan with til tail

4. Petisweda

- Pradhan karma- Virechan is given with Trivritta Avaleha 60 gms and Abhayadi modaka 250 mg 2 tab.with anupan Manuka phant.
- Patient had Samyak shuddhi with 10 vegas
- Samsarjan kram given accordingly.

• FOLLOW UP

- After every 7 days
- Mahamanjisthadi Kwath 15 ml twice a day after a meal
- Raktapachak ghan vati 250 mg twice a day after meal
- Jayapal beej lepan continued at the affected site.
- Jalaukavcharan done twice at the affected site.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

- Before Treatment: There was patchy hair loss, no hair roots, slight dryness at the site was present.
- After 2 months of treatment: No new bald patches seen, Hair fall was significantly reduced and new hair growth was seen over bald patches.

After Treatment: After 5 months treatment, length and density increased. Black hairs easily observed over most of the affected site

Before treatment

During treatment

After treatment

Arogyavardhini	Kusthaghna Pachani, Dipani, Pathya, Hridya, Medona shaka, Malashuddhikari, increase Kshudha, Sarvaroga prashamani Srotoshuddhi Contains Kutaki as the main content, which works as Shodhan and Bhendan of Dosha
Krumikuthar rasa	Karpura, Hingul, Vatsanabh, Pasash Beej, etc. mainly works on Krumi. It is considered that many Twak Vikar involve Krumi in their pathophysiology
Mahamanjishthadi Kwath	Blood purifier. It pacifies the vitiation of Kapha and Pitta and acts as a Rakta Shodhaka.
Aampachan Vati	best drug for Deepan and Pachan. Hence Aampachan Vati helps to restore healthy digestion, assimilation and metabolism of essential food elements
Jalaukavcharan	Helps in removal of vitiated Rakta.

CONCLUSION

- Virechana karma helped in detoxification of a body.
- *Arogyavardhini vati*, *Mahamanjasthadi Kwath*, *Ampachak Vati*, *Krimikuthar rasa* internally and externally use of *Jaloukavacharna* (leech therapy) was found very effective in the management of case *Indralupta*. During case study no any side effects was found. Observed benefits may be attributed to *Raktashodhak*, Antioxidant, immunomodulatory properties. *Nidanaparivarjana* was also a necessary part of the treatment.

- In this case, we observed a significant result within 4 months. This treatment protocol should be clinically evaluated on large number of patients to confirm the efficacy.

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